

Mathematics with Real-life Applications: Starting with the Big Problem

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Abstract

The author previously discussed the benefits of integrating real-world engineering applications into mathematics instruction for STEM students at the 2022 SEFI Conference (Salim, 2022). The motivation stemmed from research by Burdman (2022), which identified disengagement in traditional calculus courses as a key barrier to completing engineering degrees in the U.S. The published paper listed examples of interdisciplinary content in engineering mathematics and reported improvements in student learning and performance. We also know that traditional mathematics teaching often progresses linearly – starting with foundational concepts before advancing to complex material. This mirrors core textbook structures and may fail to engage students and adequately prepare them for later courses. Therefore, the author decided to do things differently and reorder the delivery of the content in his new work. The modified module began with the teaching of Differential Equations before introducing the foundational topics as supporting tools for solving complex engineering problems. By tackling a larger challenge first, students were encouraged to appreciate the relevance of the mathematical tools and concepts they were learning. Student feedback and performance improved compared to the previous cohorts.

Introduction

Effective learning in engineering requires a strong foundation in primary principles, science, and mathematics. Moreover, developing students' critical thinking and analytical skills is crucial for their success. A solid mathematical base is essential for nurturing competent engineers who can confidently analyse and solve problems, employ various analytical tools and techniques, effectively design and innovate solutions, and communicate their results to diverse audiences.

Recent reports, such as those by Hunter et al. (2019), suggest that disengagement with traditional calculus subjects is a significant reason for student dropout from engineering courses. Personal observations and feedback from colleagues and collaborators indicate a decline in mathematical abilities among senior undergraduate students, who struggle with even basic calculus in their advanced years. Alarming, a report titled '*Charting a New Course: Investigating Barriers on the Calculus Pathway to STEM*' (Burdman et al., 2021) further highlights that traditional approaches to calculus contribute to the discouragement of women and students from minoritised backgrounds from pursuing STEM careers. This suggests that this issue is not limited to engineering but also touches upon equity, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) in education.

Engineering educators generally agree that one of the main factors contributing to these issues is the lack of engaging and relevant material that describes, solves, and aids the understanding of the significance of mathematics in an engineering context. The report proposes that STEM academics can address these barriers to mastering mathematics by

prioritising collaborations and co-creation across disciplines to transform the teaching and learning of engineering mathematics using interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary approaches (Burdman, 2022). Studies have also shown that active learning environments are more effective than traditional lectures (Eberlein et al., 2008). Furthermore, Deakin (2006) concluded that students value the link between teaching and research, particularly research-led teaching and its impact on their learning experiences.

A paper presented by this author at the SEFI 2022 conference (Salim, 2022) outlines how active-learning and research-led teaching, with a focus on integrating multi-disciplinary content, was adopted in an existing engineering mathematics module to make it more relevant and support effective learning. This approach was well-received by students, as evidenced by positive feedback from module evaluations, surveys, and informal interviews. This encouraged the author to continue considering the importance of framing and describing the intradisciplinary nature within the mathematics syllabus, in addition to its interconnection with other engineering subjects, as recommended in the literature.

In the new paper presented here, the author details the further changes he made to the engineering mathematics module. He broke with convention and reordered the delivery of the content. Instead of teaching the syllabus in the sequence presented in core textbooks, the author started with the big problem and gradually introduced the building blocks as the semester progressed. The new approach was intended to challenge students to think more broadly and develop a better appreciation for the subject matter.

This new strategy (Version 2), together with the previous modifications discussed in the previous paper (Version 1), not only resulted in improvements in student feedback, engagement, and academic performance but also contributed towards equipping students with the skills and tools required to solve engineering challenges.

Summary of Previous Module (Version 1)

Pedagogical literature, student feedback, and discussions with educators at external events has emphasised the benefits of integrating theoretical knowledge with practical application. This informed the enhancements introduced in the first revision of the module as discussed in the 2022 paper (Salim, 2022), drawing from cross-disciplinary research and engineering subject expertise. The mathematics lessons in the module were updated with real-life applications. This aimed to help learners appreciate the relevance of mathematics in the wider engineering context, sparking their curiosity and motivating them to explore further and transfer the skills and knowledge to other subjects.

Outline of Version 1

The ‘Engineering Mathematics 2’ module is delivered to first-year undergraduate engineering students in the second semester. The topics were organised in the following sequence:

- Vectors
- Complex Numbers (CN)

- Ordinary Differential Equations (ODEs)
- Multivariate Functions (MV)
- Series and Sequences (S&S)

The topic order was consistent with the way they were presented in major textbooks, where Vectors and CN were first taught before moving to the more complex contents covering ODEs and MV, and finally S&S.

Introduction to Vectors

- Use of vectors
- What will we learn in this chapter?
 - o Basic definitions: Vector vs Scalar
 - o Coordinate Systems: Cartesian, Cylindrical and Spherical (3D). Polar (2D)
 - o Products: Dot and Cross Products
 - o Equation of a Line
 - o Equation of a Plane

Figure 1. Introductions to Vectors

Delivery of Version 1

Figure 1 shows a screenshot of the previous lecture introducing the first ‘Vectors’ topic. The lecture included examples of student projects using Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) to emphasise the relevance and importance of the topic in an engineering context. The first image shows a student modelling ventilation in a lecture theatre to assess indoor air quality in response to the COVID-19 outbreak. The other two images are simulations of an intake manifold used by the Formula Student race team and their proposed design change to enhance volumetric efficiency.

Reflections and Student Feedback in Version 1

It was evident based on student feedback that this approach engaged students, motivated them, and helped them appreciate the practical applications of vectors. The same strategy of integrating student projects highlighting real-life scenarios was applied throughout the teaching of all topics.

Below are some student comments collected as part of the formal module feedback exercise during the previous delivery. They were in response to the open-ended question:

Q: Please name the one thing in the module that had the most impact on your learning.

‘I like the variety of ways he teaches his lectures (example classes, quiz classes, polls etc) as this helps me stay engaged and focused.’

‘Lecturer is very likeable and approachable, and this shows in his lectures. Everyone pays more attention because he also makes the lectures more interesting and fun to attend.’

‘The lecturer is very engaging. He makes the lectures interesting and his passion for the subject is very clear, making lectures more enjoyable. The lectures are very interactive.’

The author attributed these positive comments to the use of real-life engineering examples to explain and bring mathematical techniques to life. By drawing in content and applications from other engineering subjects and research activities, the module became truly inter- and multi-disciplinary. Interested readers are invited to refer to the published paper (Salim, 2022) for further details, including additional examples of the integration of real-life applications and student projects.

New Strategy: Reordering Delivery of the Content (Version 2)

The author’s research expertise and interests are in Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), which includes student project supervision and numerous research publications. Since he already incorporates much of this work into his teaching to highlight real-life engineering applications, he believes it is appropriate to begin with the most intriguing and fundamental aspect, namely the Navier-Stokes (NS) equations. These are a series of differential equations that also happens to be a core component of the Engineering Mathematics 2 module.

While this approach deviates from conventional practice - since CFD and NS are typically taught in the senior years of a degree programme - the author argues that starting with the big problem and gradually introducing it at the appropriate level helps students grasp the broader picture and appreciate the relevance and importance of mathematical techniques in solving real-life engineering problems.

In the updated delivery plan, the first lesson opened with an introduction to the NS equations, highlighting their status as one of the Millennium Prize Problems by the Clay Mathematics Institute. This was followed by a discussion on various methods for solving engineering problems, including analytical, experimental, and computational approaches. The class concluded with an overview of the use of the NS equations in the context of CFD, accompanied by real-life examples from senior student projects spanning over the years.

Delivery of Version 2

The intention behind this new strategy of reordering the content is to encourage first-year students to see the wider picture and appreciate the goal of learning mathematical techniques. By gradually equipping them with the appropriate tools and skills, the author aims to adequately prepare the students in the task of analysing and solving engineering problems in later levels of studies.

Table 1 details the previous (Version 1) and reordered lesson plans (Version 2)

Table 1. Order of Topics

Topic	Version 1	Version 2
1	Vectors	Ordinary Different Equations
2	Complex Numbers	Multivariate Functions
3	Ordinary Different Equations	Complex Numbers
4	Multivariate Functions	Vectors
5	Series & Sequences	Series & Sequences

The beauty of the Navier-Stokes (NS) equations lay in their multidisciplinary nature. Students encounter them repeatedly in various forms throughout their engineering studies, particularly in Thermodynamics, Fluid Dynamics, Solid Mechanics, and other core modules. The NS equations are partial differential equations (PDEs), but for the purposes of this module, they are simplified to ordinary differential equations (ODEs). This allows for a smooth transition to other topics as the course progresses through the semester. Different aspects of the NS equation are revisited and related to the mathematical concepts being learned, thereby connecting all the contents.

Students are encouraged to take ownership of their learning by supplementing in-person lessons with virtual asynchronous learning using Pearson MyLab Math™. MyLab Math offers a combination of e-texts, homework, study plans, and online tests. Interactive example classes and discussions about engineering applications are also covered in class. To support active learning, bi-weekly class quizzes are conducted via the Pearson Learning Catalytics™ interactive digital learning resource. This technology, integrated within the Pearson MyLab Math platform, supports student engagement by generating classroom discussions, promoting peer-to-peer learning, and supporting just-in-time teaching.

Observations and Reflections in Version 2

As the semester progressed, the class performance improved as can be seen by the higher proportion of green in the pie charts for the various questions asked during the in-class tests demonstrated in Figure 2, and the class average of the continuous assessments (online tests) shown in Figure 3.

And the most impactful observation was that students performed much better in the ‘Ordinary Differential Equation’ and ‘Multivariate Functions’ related questions in the

final exam. This could be attributed to two likely factors: a) students had more time to master the more complex topics as it was introduced much earlier in the semester and b) because they started with a lower score in the in-class quiz and online test that motivated them to work harder, and as they encountered easier topics as the semester progressed this built their confidence which translated to much better engagement and outcome in the final exam. This was also reflected by the increased student satisfaction captured in the module evaluation survey.

Figure 2. Class performance in in-class quiz (conducted via Learning Catalytics)

Figure 3. Class performance in online tests (conducted via Pearson MyLab Math)

Conclusion

The gradual enhancements introduced into the module combining real-life relevance and reordering the delivery to start with the main topics clearly lead to improvements in class performance and satisfaction and could be a useful strategy to adopt in other engineering modules.

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